

Collatz Conjecture: Analytical Insights Beyond Computational Limits.

Abstract:

The Collatz conjecture, asserts that for any integer, $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, iterating the function

$$F(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ 3n + 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

The conjecture suggests that this sequence, will reach unity for all initial values, no matter how large.

Essence of the Paper: This paper is not proposing any proof of Collatz conjecture. A proof using the same methodology – modular classification, transformation rules has already been published with a DOI in this respiratory. This is rather a humble attempt to access and verify behaviour of massive integers – some of which are even beyond computational limit.

Section1: Modulo-Residual Classification of Integers:

When odd integers are classified by modulo residual class of 16 such that: $16k+m$ ($m \in 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15$) => Type 1, Type2, Type3,....Type8.

When even integers are classified by modulo residual class of 16 such that: $16k + m'$ ($m' = 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 8, 10, 12, 14$) => Ev1, Ev2, Ev3,Ev8.

Type1: $16k+1 \rightarrow 48k+4$ (by $3x+1$ operation) => Divisible by 4 ($d=4$)

Similarly, Type 2 ($16k+3$), Type 4($16k+7$), Type 6 ($16k+11$) and Type 8 ($16k+15$): $d=2$ for each type.

Type 3 ($16k+9$): $d= 16$ or 32 or more

Type 5 ($16k+9$): $d = 4$

Type 7 ($16k + 13$): $d = 8$

Section 2: Transformation:

Rule1: Type1: $16k+1 \rightarrow 48k+4$ (by $3x+1$ operation) $\rightarrow 12k+1$ (by division by 2)

The seed integer 'k' also represents Type1 to Type8 odd integers and Ev1 to Ev8. Therefore, we replace k by all odd types ($16p + a$; $a \in 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15$) and all Evs (say, $16p + a'$; $a' \in 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14$) the following types are generated: Type1 (again), Type3, Type5 and Type7 based upon the nature of k.

By similar operation on other Types a set of comprehensive transformation rules are framed.

Section 3: Transformation rules summary:

Type1 transforms into Type1 or, Type3 or, Type5 or, Type7 only.

Type 2 transforms into Type3 or Type7 only.

Type 3 transforms into all types.

Type 4 transforms into Type 2 or, Type 6 only.

Type 5 transforms into Type 2 or, Type 4 or, Type 6 or, Type 8 only.

Type 6 transforms into Type 1 or, Type 5 only.

Type 7 transforms into all types.

Types 8 transforms into Type 4 or Type 8 only.

Diagram: Visual of Modulo Residue Classes with Connectivities:

All other possibilities are mathematically ruled out and are forbidden transformations.

Demonstration of validity of transformation rules:

Even integers are being considered as intermediates between two successive odd integers.

Transformation paths are demonstrated below showing odd integers only: Iterations: $3x+1$ followed by division by 2^x (x is the appropriate power)

- Type 1: $49 (16 \times 3 + 1) \rightarrow 37 (16 \times 2 + 3: \text{Type 3}) \rightarrow 7 (16 \times 0 + 7: \text{Type 4})$.
- Type 6: $27 (16 \times 1 + 11) \rightarrow 41 (16 \times 2 + 9: \text{Type 5}) \rightarrow 31 (16 \times 1 + 15: \text{Type 8}) \rightarrow 47 (16 \times 2 + 15: \text{Type 8}) \rightarrow 71 (16 \times 4 + 7: \text{Type 4}) \rightarrow 107 (16 \times 6 + 11: \text{Type 6}) \rightarrow 161 (16 \times 10 + 1: \text{Type 1}) \rightarrow \dots$

Demonstration showing that transformations are taking place adhering to the rules.

Section 4: Customized Tool: Stepwise Synthetic Deformation of boundary integers:

Another tool we shall use to unveil underlying reasons of Collatz behaviour:

Type 8 integers having odd seed value (k) can only transform to Type 8. We take an extreme 1111... pattern Type 8 for demonstration. All such kind of integers appear as $2^{(n+1)} - 1$. Like: $31 = 2^6 - 1 = 1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 2^5$. This is the most stubborn pattern to show convergence. By stepwise synthetic deformation under Collatz operation, we shall analyze a boundary Type 8 integer, $N_0 = 2^{n+1} - 1 = (111111111... \text{ up to } n+1 \text{ terms})_2$ has a symmetrical bit pattern $= 1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^n$

$$N_1 = 3N_0 + 1 = 4 + 3 (2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^n) \text{ (Performing } 3x + 1 \text{ operation)}$$

$$\text{Or, } N_2 = 2 + 3 (1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-1}) = 5 + (2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-1}) - \text{this is evidently odd term.}$$

$$\text{Or, } N_3 = 3N_2 + 1 = 16 + 3^2 (2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-1})$$

$$\text{Or, } N_4 = 8 + 3^2 (1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-2}) = 17 + 3^2 (2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-2}) - \text{Odd term}$$

$$\text{Or, } N_5 = 3N_4 + 1 = 52 + 3^3 (2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-2})$$

Or, $N_6 = 26 + 3^3(1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-3}) = 53 + 3^3(2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-3}) - \text{Odd term}$

Or, $N_7 = 3N_6 + 1 = 160 + 3^4(2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-3})$

Or, $N_8 = 80 + 3^4(1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-4}) = 161 + 3^4(2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \dots + 2^{n-4}) - \text{Odd term.}$

A closer look at the integers generated as odd terms reveals that, they bear a common form of $2 \cdot 3^{x+1} - 1$, like, $2 \cdot 3^2 - 1 = 17$, $2 \cdot 3^3 - 1 = 53$, $2 \cdot 3^4 - 1 = 161$ at every $(2n-1)^{\text{th}}$ step.

At some point of time all powers of 2 will be exhausted. This can be interpreted as, all $2^{n+1} - 1$ type integers produce $2 \cdot 3^n - 1$ type integer at every $(2n-1)^{\text{th}}$ step which on further iteration transform into $3^n - 1$ type of even integers usually having high divisibility. Table given below depicts some reality checks over the fact mentioned above:

Table:1

n	$2^{n+1} - 1$	$(3^{n+1} - 1)/2^x$	Type of $(3^n - 1)/2^x$	Number of steps taken to generate
4	31	121	Type 1	10+1
5	63	91	Type 6	12+3
6	127	1093	Type 3	14+1
7	255	205	Type 7	16+5
8	511	9841	Type1	18+1
9	1023	7381	Type 3	20+3
16	393214	64570081	Type 1	34+1
21	4194303	1961316225	Type 1	44+4

Section 5: Some Tangible Results:

With the modular classes and transformation rules, it is possible to identify **unstable non-trivial loops** proving a universal convergence. That aspect has been explained in previous publications and not in the scope of this paper.

Mathematicians have been using computational verification techniques to test whether very large numbers behave abnormally. Supercomputers probably has validated many results using efficient programming codes. However, in this paper we shall display some mathematical techniques to examine behaviour of integers enormous in size.

A. Demonstration of the largest number verified for Collatz conjecture:

According to web, the largest number verified = $2^{100000} - 1$.

A binary expression of $31 = 11111$: $2^4 + 2^3 + 2^2 + 2 + 1 = 2^4 + 15 \Rightarrow$ last four 1's represent 15. All other 1's in such pattern represent for $2^4 + 2 \times 2^4 + 4 \times 2^4 + 8 \times 2^4 + \dots$

All type8 integers of such pattern can be presented as $2^n - 1 = 16(2^{n-4} - 1) + 15$

Therefore, $2^{100000} - 1 = 16(2^{99996} - 1) + 15$

This, after $(2 \times 100000 - 1) = 199999$ steps will be converted to $2 \times 3^{10000} - 1$, and in the very next step this will again converted to $3^{100000} - 1$. It follows that, if $2^{100000} - 1$ is verified by a supercomputer as the largest Collatz integer, **then even a larger integer $3^{100000} - 1$ is verified as Collatz integer without brute force or without aid of a supercomputer.**

B. Enormous Numbers With Shortest Path of Convergence:

The shortest route to convergence is widely discussed $\frac{2^{2n}-1}{3}$ ($n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$) Some examples: 5, 21, 341 ...

These are all $16k+5$ i.e Type 3 integers. As per transformation rules, shortest routes to Type 3 are:

- 1) Type 1 to Type 3, 2) Type 2 to 3, 3) Type 3, 4) Type 4 to Type 2 to Type 3,
- 5) Type 5 to Type 2 to Type 3, 6) Type 6 to Type 1 to Type 3, 7) Type 7 to Type 3,
- 8) Type 8 to Type 4 to Type 2 to Type 3.

We'll form mathematical equations for all transformations. To establish the principle, let's demonstrate the last and the longest route:

Step I: Type 8: $16k+5 \rightarrow 24k+23$ ($3x+1$ followed by division by 2) \Rightarrow This is Type 4

Step II: $24k+23 \rightarrow 36k+35 \Rightarrow$ This is Type 2

Step III: $36k+35 \rightarrow 54k+53 \Rightarrow$ This is Type 3

To adopt the shortest path, Type 3 must be $= \frac{2^{2n}-1}{3} = 54k+53$

Solving, $16k+5 = \frac{2^{2n+3}-65}{81}$ in the equation, n has a periodicity $= 14 + 27m$ ($m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$) and after a few iterations, it reaches 2^{2n} . 2^{2n} takes $2n$ more steps to reach 1.

All integers in this scope are necessarily Type 8 and follow the shortest convergence route to unity. Let's verify:

For $m=0$, $n=14$, $\frac{2^{2n+3}-65}{81}$ gives $= 26512143 = 16 \times 1657008 + 15$ - a Type 8 integer.

Convergence of 26512143 will have 3 more odd integers (Type 4, Type 2 and Type 3) and 3 more odd integer in between before reaching 2^{28} .

For $m=1$, $n=41$ $\frac{2^{2n+3}-65}{81}$ gives $= 477600323798372019637007$ - a Type 8 integer.

Convergence of this huge number will have 3 more odd integers (Type 4, Type 2 and Type 3) and 3 more odd integer in between before reaching 2^{82} .

477600323798372019637007 \rightarrow **1432800971395116058911022** (even) - By $3x+1$

1432800971395116058911022 \rightarrow **716400485697558029455511** (odd: Type 4) by division by 2

716400485697558029455511 \rightarrow **2149201457092674088366534** (even)

2149201457092674088366534 \rightarrow **1074600728546337044183267** (odd: Type 2)

1074600728546337044183267 \rightarrow **3223802185639011132549802** (even)

3223802185639011132549802 \rightarrow **1611901092819505566274901** (odd: Type 3)

1611901092819505566274901 \rightarrow **4835703278458516698824707** (even) $= 2^{82}$

These 24 digit odd numbers of quintillion magnitude can be predicted without any computational validation. Next number in this series comes up with a dimension of 2^{139} and behaves in the same way.

Other sets are also listed in the following for future reference:

$$1) \text{ Type 1} = \frac{2^{2n+2}-7}{9} \quad n = 3m+1 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$2) \text{ Type 2} = \frac{2^{2n+1}-5}{9} \quad n = 3m+2 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$3) \text{ Type 3} = \frac{2^{2n}-1}{3} \quad n = 3m+2 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$4) \text{ Type 4} = \frac{2^{2n+2}-19}{27} \quad n = 9m+5 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$5) \text{ Type 5} = \frac{2^{2n+3}-29}{27} \quad n = 9m + 8 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$6) \text{ Type 6} = \frac{2^{2n+3}-2}{27} \quad n = 9m + 4 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

$$7) \text{ Type 7} = \frac{2^{2n+3}-11}{9} \quad n = 3m + 2 \quad (m \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$$

Conclusion: In addition to computational methods, modulo- residue classes are also useful in validating integers of enormous size. This work reinforces the conjecture's validity and offers new insights beyond computational approaches refraining all possibilities in a deterministic framework.

Bibliography

1. Lagarias, J. C. (2010). *The Ultimate Challenge: The 3x+1 Problem*. American Mathematical Society.
 2. Wirsching, G. J. (1998). *The Dynamical System Generated by the 3n + 1 Function*. Springer.
 3. Terras, R. (1976). "A Stopping Time Problem on the Positive Integers." *Acta Arithmetica*, 30(3), 241–252.
 4. Everett, C. J. (1977). "Iteration of the Number-Theoretic Function $f(2n) = n$, $f(2n + 1) = 3n + 2$." *Advances in Mathematics*, 25(1), 42–45.
 5. Oliveira e Silva, T. (2010). "Empirical Verification of the 3x+1 Conjecture for Large Integers." *Mathematics of Computation*, 79(270), 1201–1220.
 6. Ren, W., Li, L., Xu, M., & Bai, X. (2018). *Collatz Conjecture for 2100000–12^{100000}-12100000–1 Is True - Algorithms for Verifying Extremely Large Numbers*. In *Proceedings of the 15th IEEE International Conference on Ubiquitous Intelligence and Computing (UIC)*, Guangzhou, China, October 2018. [IEEE Xplore](#)
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